

The Mediating Effect of Service Quality in Relation to Corporate Social Responsibility and Customer-Based Brand Equity

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ABSTRACT: *The primary goal of this research was to investigate the role of service quality in mediating the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and customer-based brand equity (CBBE) in tourism businesses in the Davao Region. The study utilized the quantitative non-experimental descriptive and correlational research design. There were 176 tourism enterprises surveyed for the independent variable of CSR determined by proportionate stratified sampling. Meanwhile, 384 tourists were also surveyed for the mediator variable of Service Quality and the independent variable of CBBE derived through snowball sampling. Google forms were employed to gather the primary data on the three variables of the study. The multiple regression analysis indicated that CSR predicted CBBE, CSR predicted Service Quality, and combined CSR and Service Quality statistically predicted CBBE. In the relationship between CSR and CBBE, the mediation study revealed partial mediation of Service Quality. The Medgraph pathway illustrated that Service Quality intervened with the effects that CSR had on CBBE. Service Quality statistically significantly reduced the total effect of CSR on CBBE. Thus, not only should CSR be improved, but Service Quality also needs to be enhanced for Davao Region to become a top tourism destination in the Philippines and Southeast Asia.*

Keywords: *tourism, hospitality management, CSR, CBBE, Service Quality, multiple regression, mediation, Medgraph, Philippines*

I. INTRODUCTION

International perceptions of Mindanao's safety and security concerns have harmed Davao Region's customer-based brand equity as a tourism destination (Japan International Cooperation Agency 2018). Thus, the customer-based brand equity of the Davao Region is negatively impacted by the perceived instability of regional peace and order (Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation 2017). It has fostered apprehensions among international tourists regarding travel to Davao Region (Arellano 2019), leading to a decline in international travelers (Philippine Statistics Authority 2019). Furthermore, customer-based brand equity for the Davao Region as a tourism destination has not been investigated (Department of Tourism 2017). These are urgent and important issues for the tourism and hospitality industry of Davao Region due to the need to propel Davao Region into becoming the competitively dominant destination among competing for regional destinations in the Philippines (National Economic and Development Authority, 2017).

Customer-based brand equity for tourism destinations spurs prospective tourists to visit a destination (Dedeoglu et al., 2019). Positive brand equity for tourism destinations is an essential metric for improving tourism and hospitality services and products to achieve substantial competitive dominance over other tourism destinations that will be sustainable over time (Department of Tourism 2017). Such dominance in position as the preferred tourism destination will enable a tourism destination to carve a bigger market share, design a favorable tourism destination brand image, and maintain loyalty among tourists (Herrero-Crespo et al., 2017). The service quality of tourism enterprises is a valuable economic impetus for countries (Park & Jeong 2019). The service quality of tourism enterprises is judged by tourists and will be the basis for return visits and recommendations to others (Eshetie et al., 2016). It is thus considered a significant core concept and a critical success factor in the tourism industry. A successful tourism enterprise in a successful tourism destination delivers excellent quality service to customers. As a result, improving the quality of service given by tourism businesses is the backbone of any tourism destination (Department of Tourism 2017). CSR for sustainable tourism has a positive impact on tourist destination aspects such as brand image, perceived quality, brand awareness, and brand loyalty (Bediako 2017; Chubchuwong 2019; Gudjonsdottir&Jusubova 2015; Martínez & Nishiyama

2019; Mohammed & Al-Swidi 2019). CSR for sustainable tourism was found to positively correlate with satisfaction on service quality of tourism enterprises and tourism destinations (Bashir & Amir 2019; Kim & Kim 2016; Latif et al. 2020). Customer-based brand equity tourist destination characteristics were directly influenced by tourism firms and destinations (Dahiya & Batra 2017; Khuong&Duyen 2017; Su et al. 2016; Virkar& Mallya 2018).

When Latif et al. (2020) investigated CSR in strengthening brand equity as mediated by service quality, they discovered the mediating influence of service quality of tourism companies and tourism destinations on CSR for sustainable tourism on customer-based brand equity tourism destination aspects. The link between CSR and brand equity was found to be significantly mediated by service quality. The studies mentioned and the mandate of RA 9593 or The Tourism Act of 2009 to formulate a Tourism Development Plan for Davao Region as a cluster tourism destination (Department of Tourism 2017) became the impetus for this current research. To date, no studies on CSR for sustainable tourism, service quality of tourism businesses, or customer-based brand equity of the Davao Region as a tourism destination have been conducted. After the COVID-19 epidemic, the global tourism sector will rebound in the next two years (Asian Development Bank 2020). The Davao Region must be well equipped as a tourism destination for this. This study will look into the CSR for sustainable tourism, the service quality of tourism businesses, and the customer-based brand equity of the Davao Region as a tourist destination. This research study will fill a significant research gap on Davao Region as a tourism destination while also meeting an urgent need to evaluate tourism enterprises in Davao Region in terms of their CSR for sustainable tourism, service quality, and tourism destination customer-based brand equity. This study may then contribute to the revitalization of the tourism industry in Davao Region.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative non-experimental research design that was descriptive and correlational and the survey technique. Quantitative non-experimental research design is a deductive approach towards research that involves gathering and analyzing data utilizing methods based on Mathematics (Almalki 2016). This was appropriate for this study because the researcher aimed to measure sustainable tourism corporate social responsibility, tourism enterprise service quality, and tourism destination customer-based brand equity in the Davao Region.

The quantitative research design was descriptive because it characterized and interpreted the current conditions of sustainable tourism, corporate social responsibility, tourism enterprise service quality, and tourism destination customer-based brand equity in the Davao Region (Mertler 2018). This study was also correlational because it utilized the statistical procedure of multiple regression analysis. This was to reach conclusions about the predictive association between and among the variables of the study. Additionally, such statistical procedure tested the hypotheses of the study (Ali & Bhaskar 2016). In this study, the survey technique provided a numeric description of the level of sustainable tourism corporate social responsibility, tourism enterprise service quality, and tourism destination customer-based brand equity in the Davao Region (Creswell & Creswell 2017).

Furthermore, mediation analysis is a method of statistically examining how an independent variable or another causal factor affects changes in the outcome variable. Testing for mediation is a critical component in the analysis of causal research models. This was appropriate for the study because it looked at the interaction effects of CSR and service quality on CBBE among tourism businesses in the Davao Region.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULT

As Table 1 presents, CSR (N = 176) overall mean was 1.97 ($SD = 0.18$, $SE = 0.43$). This had a descriptive level of Low. Social practices were the CSR indicator with the highest mean at 2.21 ($SD = 0.12$, $SE = 0.43$). While this represented the highest mean among CSR indicators, the descriptive level was still categorized as Low. The CSR indicator with the lowest mean was environmental practices with 1.83 ($SD = 0.16$, $SE = 0.43$). This also had an interpretation of having a Low descriptive level.

Table 1
Corporate Social Responsibility of Davao Region Tourism Enterprises

Indicators	M	SD	Descriptive Level
Environmental Practices	1.83	0.16	Low
Social Practices	2.21	0.12	Low
Economic Practices	1.87	0.26	Low
Overall Mean	1.97	0.18	Low

Note. M = Mean; SD = standard deviation

CBBE (N = 384) overall mean was 2.04 (SD = 0.24, SE = 0.43). The overall descriptive level for CBBE was Low. Awareness was the CBBE indicator with the highest mean of 2.51 (SD = 0.22, SE = 0.43). Even though this was the CBBE indicator with the highest mean, it still had a descriptive level of Low. The CBBE indicator with the lowest mean was loyalty (M = 1.60, SD = 0.26, SE = 0.43). The CBBE indicator of loyalty had a descriptive level of Very Low. Table 2 presents these results.

Table 2
Customer-Based Brand Equity of Davao Region as a Tourism Destination

Indicators	M	SD	Descriptive Level
Value	1.83	0.24	Low
Quality	2.22	0.24	Low
Awareness	2.51	0.22	Low
Loyalty	1.60	0.26	Very Low
Overall Mean	2.04	0.24	Low

Note. N = number of valid observations for CBBE; M = Mean; SD = standard deviation; SE = standard error associated with the mean

Presented in Table 3 is Service Quality (N = 384) overall mean of 1.99 (SD = 0.18, SE = 0.43). The overall mean had a descriptive level of Low. The Service quality indicator of Assurance-Responsiveness got the highest mean of 2.16 (SD = 0.19, SE = 0.43). While it had the highest mean among the three indicators of Service Quality, it had a descriptive level of Low. Reliability-Quality was the indicator with the lowest mean (M = 1.83, SD = 0.18, SE = 0.43). This had a descriptive level of Low.

Table 3
Service Quality of Davao Region Tourism Enterprises

Indicators	M	SD	Descriptive Level
Assurance-Responsiveness	2.16	0.19	Low
Tangible Facilities-Empathy	1.98	0.17	Low
Reliability-Quality	1.83	0.18	Low
Overall Mean	1.99	0.18	Low

Note. N = number of valid observations for Service Quality; M = Mean; SD = standard deviation; SE = standard error associated with the mean

Presented in Table 4 is the result of the bivariate regression analysis to predict Service Quality based on CSR. A positive and statistically significant regression equation was found ($F(1,175) = 9.755, p=.004$), with an R^2 of 0.258, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. It can be predicted that Service Quality will be equal to $0.966 + 0.517$ (CSR) Service Quality Likert-scale values when CSR is measured with a similar scale. Service Quality will increase by 0.517 for each Likert-scale value of CSR.

Table 4

Regression Coefficients of the Independent and Mediating Variables

Variables	B	t	p	Decision on H ₀
CSR > CBBE	0.597	2.697	0.012*	Reject
CSR > SVCQ	0.517	3.123	0.004*	Reject
SVCQ > CBBE	0.794	4.113	0.000*	Reject

Note. CSR > CBBE = Corporate Social Responsibility effect on Customer-Based Brand Equity; CSR > SVCQ = Corporate Social Responsibility effect on Service Quality; SVCQ > CBBE = Service Quality effect on Customer-Based Brand Equity; B = unstandardized coefficient; SE = standard error associated with the unstandardized coefficient; t = t-value; *p < 0.05; CI = confidence interval.

Lastly, Table 4 informs of the output of the bivariate regression analysis on the predictive value of Service Quality on CBBE. A positive and statistically significant regression equation was found ($F(1,383) = 16.916, p = .000$), with an R² of 0.377, leading to the null hypothesis being rejected. It can be predicted that CBBE will be equal to $0.461 + 0.794$ (Service Quality) CBBE Likert-scale values when Service Quality is measured with a similar scale. CBBE will increase 0.517 for each Likert-scale value of Service Quality.

Table 5 shows the impact of the interaction effects of Corporate Social Responsibility and Service Quality on Customer-Based Brand Equity of Davao Region as a tourism destination. In Model 1 of the Stepwise Regression, the R² value of 0.206 revealed that CSR explained approximately 21% of the variance in CBBE, significant with a p-value of .012. In Model 2, wherein the joint impact of CSR and Service Quality was incorporated, the R² value of 0.404 indicated that CSR and Service Quality explained approximately 40% of the variance in CBBE, significant with a p-value of .006. The ΔR^2 value of 0.198 specified a 19.8% change in the variance of Model 1 and Model 2, significant with a p-value of .006.

The results of the regression further revealed that CSR ($\beta = 0.192, p = 0.276$) and Service Quality ($\beta = 0.516, p = 0.006$) positively predicted CBBE. The regression weights for CSR were subsequently reduced from Model 1 to Model 2, with β values from 0.454 in Model 1 to 0.192 in Model 2. This was not statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.276. This result confirmed the partial mediation of Service Quality in the relationship between CSR and CBBE. More specifically, CSR has direct as well as indirect effects on CBBE, mediated by Service Quality.

Table 5

Regression Analysis for Mediation of Service Quality between Corporate Social Responsibility and Customer-Based Brand Equity

Variable	B	SE	95% CI	β	p	R ²	ΔR^2
Model 1					0.012	0.206	0.206*
Constant	0.859*	0.439	[-0.04, 1.76]		0.060		
Corporate Social Responsibility	0.597*	0.221	[0.14, 1.05]	0.454	0.012		
Model 2					0.006	0.404	0.198*
Constant	0.214	0.443	[-0.70, 1.12]		0.633		
Corporate Social Responsibility	0.252	0.227	[-0.21, 0.72]	0.192	0.276		

IV. DISCUSSION

CSR

Through CSR, tourism enterprises voluntarily integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and their interactions with their stakeholders. This research found that the level of CSR among tourism enterprises in the Davao Region was low. The standard deviation signified that CSR values reported by the Davao Region tourism enterprises were not very dispersed.

The low mean value of the Social Practices of CSR does not bode well for the Davao Region tourism enterprises. The evaluation of social practices is founded upon the societal effect of the business (Tran et al., 2018). Hence, Davao Region tourism enterprises' low impact on the populace would not encourage support towards these tourism enterprises, as expounded upon by Chilufya et al. (2019) and Sanfiel-Fumero et al. (2017) on their research on CSR. The low mean of the economic practices CSR indicator also has negative implications for Davao Region tourism enterprises. This is because economic practices exemplify good relations with local communities (Mgonja et al., 2015).

Moreover, it has been an essential measure for sustainable tourism (Nunthasiriphon 2015). Thus, because of this low mean for economic practices, Davao Region tourism enterprises will have difficulty encouraging the community as stakeholders in positively collaborating with them (International Labour Organization 2017). This result is similar to the research outcomes of Contreiras et al. (2016).

Moreover, the low mean for CSR indicators of environmental practices is negative for Davao Region tourism enterprises. This is because environmental practices are initiatives that contribute to environmental conservation (Yang et al. 2020). With people's greater awareness for environmental protection, environmental practices reflect on the conscience of tourism enterprises (Baniya et al. 2019; Camilleri 2020) and are perceived as metrics for concern not only for the environment but for the stakeholders as well (Ibarnia et al. 2020; Paskova&Zelenka 2019).

CBBE

Favorable CBBE is a crucial tool for upping the competitive advantage of tourism destinations. CBBE improves the position of the tourism destination and, more importantly, influences the choices that tourists make in their travel decisions (Su et al., 2016). The finding of this research was that CBBE of Davao Region as a tourism destination was low. This research also determined that the idea of Davao Region tourists regarding Davao Region as a brand is not very varied and that this study's sample of tourists was a microcosmic representation of the population of Davao Region tourists.

Davao Region as a tourism destination was not popular among tourists, whether local or international, as reflected in the low mean of CBBE indicator of awareness. Thus, it can be inferred that branding of Davao Region as a tourism destination had not been effective (Duman et al., 2018). This is not productive for Davao Region as a tourism destination because awareness is the first crucial facet of attracting tourists (Ahn& Back 2017). Additionally, the Quality of a tourism destination could not be tested in the absence of Awareness (Dedeoglu et al. 2019). Dismally, the Quality of CBBE of Davao Region as a tourism destination was at a low level. Quality is the perception of tourists regarding a tourism destination (Pike & Bianchi 2016), and the finding of this research implying that tourists who had been to Davao Region rated the Quality of the region as low has a consequential impact on whether or not they would become repeat clients and whether or not they would recommend Davao Region to family, friends, and acquaintances. This is congruent with the research outcomes of Seric et al. (2018).

Furthermore, the value that tourists who had been to Davao Region placed on the geo-political area was low. This is also detrimental to the image of Davao Region as a tourism destination because this manifested their view of Davao Region as a tourist destination that did not have a good return for money expended. This is supported by the study of Kim & Lee (2018) and the findings of Kladou et al. (2016). Therefore, it was not surprising that tourists who had visited Davao Region did not have a sense of loyalty towards the region as a tourism destination. It had the lowest mean among the four CBBE indicators. This means that tourists did not feel any affiliation with Davao Region and its brand as a tourism destination. This was in concordance with the findings of Tosun et al. (2015).

Service Quality

Service quality has been identified as an essential driver of tourism (Park & Jeong 2019). Additionally, it has been recognized as the primary impetus in developing a huge advantage for the tourism service industry (Lai et al., 2017). The outcome of this study was that the Service Quality of tourism enterprises in the Davao Region was low. The

implication is that tourists did not experience satisfaction with the services that Davao Region tourism enterprises provided to them, similar to the results of the research of Lee et al. (2016). The tourists did not sense that the services they had experienced and expected were at par with their expectations. This is comparable with the study of Ahrhold et al. (2017). This also means that, for the tourists, the tourism personnel, their services, and the tourism products were not competent enough compared to other tourism destinations. This was analogous to the findings of Eshetie et al. (2016). This was reflected in the Service Quality indicator of Assurance-Responsiveness, which had a low mean.

Moreover, the tourists did not perceive that the tourism facilities of Davao Region were competitive with other tourism destinations. This was evident in the low Tangible Facilities-Empathy indicator of Service Quality, which had a low mean. The physical facilities of Davao Region, such as airport transfers, public transportation, tourist road guides to tourist destinations, and many more, did not meet the expectations of tourists. This result coincides with Al-Ababneh's (2017) conclusions and Sharmin et al.'s (2016) on the impact of the features and conditions of tangible facilities on the perception of the Quality of tourism services. Therefore, it is no wonder that tourists did not feel confident in the Service Quality of Davao Region as a tourism destination, expressed in the indicator of Reliability-Quality, which also had a low mean. This suggests that tourists who had traveled to Davao Region did not experience consistency in the dependability of services. This implication is consistent with various studies (Mmutle&Shonhe 2017; Zgolli&Zaiem 2017).

Predictive Value of CSR on CBBE, CSR on Service Quality, Service Quality on CBBE

The findings on the predictive value of CSR on CBBE, CSR on Service Quality, and Service Quality on CBBE, which were all statistically significant, confirm the existing literature on the role of CSR on CBBE, CSR on Service Quality, and Service Quality on CBBE. That CSR predicts CBBE was determined by Martínez and Nishiyama (2019), Gudjonsdottir and Jusubova (2015), Chubchuwong (2019), Mohammed, and Al-Swidi (2019), and Bediako (2017). Hence, this predictive value of CSR needs to be the basis for Davao Region tourism enterprises to strengthen their CBBE via increasing their CSR.

Additionally, the predictive value of CSR on Service Quality has positive implications on the probability of enhancing the Service Quality of Davao Region tourism enterprises (Kim 2016; Latif et al. 2020). Heightening the implementation of CSR activities of tourism enterprises will increase Service Quality (Bashir & Amir 2019). Moreover, Service Quality was found to predict CBBE. This has the strongest impact on the factors that determine whether or not local or international tourists will become attracted to Davao Region as a tourism destination (Virkar& Mallya 2018). Improving the Service Quality of tourism destinations will directly impact the perceptions of tourists towards the Davao Region (Kim & Kim 2016; Su et al. 2016). Service Quality should be considered by Davao Region tourism destinations as the core value of their services due to its strong influence on CBBE (Dahiya & Batra 2017; Khuong&Duyen 2017).

Mediating Effect of Service Quality on the Relationship between CSR and CBBE

The model proposed by this research effectively facilitated predictions regarding CSR, CBBE, and Service Quality that approximated the real data points for these variables. This was evidenced by the value of the R^2 that indicated that 40% of the variance in CBBE could be explained by CSR and Service Quality. The ΔR^2 also conveyed that the addition of Service Quality to CSR as a factor to CBBE would increase the variance in CBBE by 49%; the ΔR^2 could be attributed to Service Quality. The gravity and extent of the effect of Service Quality on CBBE were further supported by investigating the standardized values of CSR and CBBE. The absolute β value for Service Quality was more than twice that of CSR. This rendered the fact that Service Quality was more than twice relevant as CSR in predicting the values of CBBE.

The mediation analysis determined that not only did Service Quality have prodigious effects on CBBE, but that it also intervened with the effects that CSR had on CBBE. The Medgraph pathway analysis signified that Service Quality decreased the capability of CSR by more than half, a significant 58.79% reduction of its total effect. This mediation, albeit only partial, could nevertheless statistically significantly be classified as large. Importantly, this large partial mediation of Service Quality deducted more than half of the effectiveness of CSR as a contributory variable to CBBE. This result has far-reaching implications for the decision-making of the Davao Region tourism enterprises. The mediating effect of Service Quality on the relationship between CSR and CBBE needs to be a guiding principle in cultivating Davao Region as the premier tourism destination not only in the Philippines but also in Southeast Asia.

The overall results of this research supported the assertion of the Stakeholder Theory of CSR (Freeman & Werhane 2005) that organizational accountability is not limited simply to economic and financial performance but also

stakeholders such as the community and the clientele. Furthermore, this study's findings also expanded the breadth of the scope of SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al. 1988) by applying the theory to the tourism and hospitality industry in the geographical context of the Davao Region and its tourism enterprises. Finally, this research confirmed the Destination Brand Equity Theory (Boo et al. 2009) that the new construct of destination brand experience could be quantified through the dimensions of value, Quality, awareness, and loyalty.

CONCLUSION

Founded upon the results of this study, this research concludes the following:

The overall level of CSR among tourism enterprises in the Davao Region was low. This implied that its indicators of environmental practices, social practices, and economic practices were seldom practiced. Additionally, the overall level of CBBE of Davao Region as a tourism destination was also found below. This signified that destination brand value, Quality, awareness, and loyalty of Davao Region were seldom evident among the local and international tourists who had visited the region. Moreover, the overall level of Service Quality of tourism enterprises in the Davao Region was low. This indicated that this study seldom demonstrated assurance-responsiveness, tangible facilities-empathy, and reliability quality by the Davao Region tourism enterprises investigated. Furthermore, this research revealed that changes in the causal variables predicted changes in the outcome variables: CSR predicted CBBE, CSR predicted Service Quality, and Service Quality predicted CBBE. Finally, this study established that Service Quality mediated the relationship between CSR and CBBE.

It can be inferred from the results that the conceptual model proposed by this study is a viable research model that could be practically utilized in investigating the variables included in this research. Importantly, this study reinforced the propositions of Stakeholder Theory of CSR (Freeman & Werhane 2005) by demonstrating that the low level of CSR among the tourism enterprises in Davao Region affected the primary stakeholders of tourism and hospitality: the local and international tourists who were the clients of these business entities. This study also buttressed the relevance of SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al. 1988) as a foundational theory for investigations into service quality. This research accomplished this by contributing to the applicability of the theory to the tourism and hospitality industry of the Davao Region. Finally, the results of this study affirmed the advocated dimensions of Destination Brand Equity Theory (Boo et al. 2009) as essential measures of CBBE of Davao Region as a tourism destination.

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